

MULTIFUNCTIONAL STRUCTURAL CAPACITORS CONSISTING OF BARIUM TITANATE AND BARIUM STRONTIUM TITANATE COATED CARBON FIBERS

Y. Lin¹, Z. Zhi², J. Romero³ and H.A. Sodano^{1,2*}

¹ Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, University of Florida, Gainesville, FL, U.S.A., ² Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Florida, Gainesville, FL, U.S.A. ³ School for Engineering of Matter, Transport and Energy, Arizona State University, Tempe, AZ, U.S.A.

* Corresponding author (hsodano@ufl.edu)

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1 Introduction

The increasing demand for high efficiency and lightweight systems has led to the emergence of multifunctional materials. This class of materials combines the performance objectives of two or more components of a system into a single material. For instance, additional functionalities such as ballistic protection,[1] vibration damping,[2] energy generation and storage,[3-5] sensing and actuation,[6-7] self healing,[8-9] and thermal management[10] have all been incorporated into structural composites. The use of the multifunctional materials can increase the safety and performance while holding the weight and complexity to a minimum.

One of the benefits of using multifunctional composites is that the operational efficiency can be improved through the integration and distribution of energy generation and storage components into the structure. Multifunctional composites with both energy harvesting and storage capacity have drawn great interest because the useful mission duration of vehicles is limited by the energy density of the entire system. [11] Specifically, Unmanned Air Vehicles (UAV) need a material capable of power harvesting, minimal weight and energy storage to both provide power to intermittent demands and to further reduce the system size. [12]

Thomas et al. embedded commercial polymer lithium-ion cells into a carbon epoxy composite of a Wasp micro-air vehicle and observed a 26% increase in flight endurance time. [13] Pereira et al. [14] developed a laminated structural carbon fiber composite by embedding solid-state thin film lithium energy cells into carbon fiber polymer composites without significantly impacting the

composites mechanical properties. The performance of the embedded energy cells was not degraded under up to 50% of the composites tensile strength. Recently, Neudecker et al. [15] coated a single carbon fiber filament with multi-layer lithium thin film battery components to form a thin film structural battery that was embedded into a composite system. A patch consisting of 1000-coated fibers could output 9W at 3V and 3A while supplying 0.1Wh of energy. Although embedding of the lithium ion based battery prolonged the systems operation, the poor mechanical properties of the polymer battery degraded the material properties of the entire system.

Recently, Lin and Sodano developed an active structural fiber that combined strong piezoelectric coupling with load bearing properties. [16-17] The fiber was fabricated through the deposition of a barium titanate shell on a SiC fiber. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the active fiber developed. The authors utilized this fiber for energy storage and demonstrated electromechanical coupling nearly two orders of magnitude greater than existing structural capacitors developed based on glass or polymer fiber composites. In this paper, a new synthesis procedure will be developed for barium strontium titanate ($\text{Ba}_x\text{Sr}_{1-x}\text{TiO}_3$ or BST) and demonstrated on carbon fiber substrates. The significantly reduced fiber size presents significant challenges to the fabrication and thus a novel hydrothermal process has been developed. In this paper the energy storage characteristics of the fiber will be studied for various stoichiometric compositions of the barium strontium titanate (barium to strontium ratio). Both the dielectric permittivity and strength are measured and used to identify the energy density of the specimens. The

dielectric constant values are calculated and compared with the theoretical values while the breakdown voltages of the multifunctional fibers are tested according to ASTM standard (ASTM D 149-97a). [18] The results demonstrate a novel process which can reduce the fiber size while maintaining the same energy density as that obtained with the 28 times larger fiber.

Fig. 1. Schematic showing of the cross-section of the multifunctional fiber.

2 Experimental details

The fabrication of $Ba_xSr_{1-x}TiO_3$ film on carbon fiber is approached by a two-step hydrothermal reaction, as illustrated in Figure 2. First, TiO_2 nanowire arrays are coated onto carbon fiber filament (IM8, Hexcel) using the similar method as mentioned elsewhere [19], leaving a 1cm long section uncoated for using as testing leads. A typical SEM image of the TiO_2 nanowires grown on carbon fibers is shown in Figure 3. After the TiO_2 nanowires were grown on the carbon fiber, it was then transferred to $Ba_xSr_{1-x}TiO_3$ by reaction with $Ba(OH)_2 \cdot 8H_2O$, $Sr(OH)_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ aqueous solution. In order to study the influence of the barium and strontium ratio in determining the energy density of the film, 7 different ratios of $Ba_xSr_{1-x}TiO_3$ were fabricated and a 10 nm gold coating was sputtered on the BST film for testing (Pelco SC-7). After that, a bare carbon fiber and BST with gold coating were connected to external leads for dielectric and breakdown strength testing.

Fig. 2. Flow chart of the fabrication process of BST coated multifunctional fiber.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Microstructure and crystal structure

Typical SEM images of carbon fibers coated with TiO_2 nanowires and BST film coating are shown in Figure 3. According to Figure 3a, the length of the nanowires is about $7\mu m$ while the diameter of the TiO_2 nanowire is approximately 200nm. After the transferring of TiO_2 nanowires to barium strontium titanate, the nanowires fuse together creating a continuous film as shown in Figure 3b. This growth of the crystals during the transformation from TiO_2 to $Ba_xSr_{1-x}TiO_3$ has been found in a similar synthesis process of BST particles [19] Figure 3c, shows the BST film has a high density with no voids or cracks. In order to confirm the TiO_2 nanowires have been fully transformed to BST, the crystal structure before and after transfer to barium titanate or barium strontium titanate is characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD). The XRD trace is shown in Figure 4 and demonstrates the peak shift with an increase strontium concentration. The upward shift occurs because the lattice spacing of strontium titanate (3.905\AA) is smaller than that of barium titanate (4.038\AA), which according to Bragg's law produces diffraction at higher angles with increasing strontium. [20] The XRD spectrums of transferred BSTs do not contain any peaks from TiO_2 , thus indicating the films are fully transferred, which is critical for high energy density since TiO_2 has a low dielectric.

3.2 Sample preparation of dielectric testing

When designing a structural capacitor, the most important factor is its energy density, which is defined as the ratio of the maximum stored electrostatic energy to the total volume of the capacitor. The energy stored in a dielectric capacitor is defined by the following equation

$$U = \frac{1}{2} CV^2 \quad (1)$$

where U is the stored electrical energy, C is the capacitance, and V is the voltage applied on the capacitor. Therefore, maximum energy density is typically achieved by increasing the dielectric strength of the capacitor. The multifunctional fiber described here can be considered to be a concentric cylinder capacitor since the carbon fiber core acts as

Fig. 3. SEM images of multifunctional fiber, (a) TiO₂ nanowires coated carbon fiber, (b) BST coated carbon fiber, (c) cross section of BST coated carbon fiber.

Fig. 4. XRD scan of various BST films on carbon fibers.

one electrode. The capacitance of this form of capacitor is expressed as

$$C = \frac{2\pi\kappa\epsilon_0 L}{\ln(b/a)} \quad (2)$$

where ϵ_0 is the permittivity of free space (8.85×10^{-12}), κ is the relative dielectric constant, L is the length of multifunctional fiber, b is the radius of the multifunctional fiber, and a is the radius of carbon fiber. It can be seen by Equation (2) that the capacitance is a function of the relative dielectric constant and sample geometry. Therefore, when considering samples with the same geometry, the capacitance is dependent on the dielectric permittivity of the specimen. An LCR meter (Agilent E4980A) was used to measure the capacitance of individual multifunctional fibers with various BST compositions. After the dielectric of each sample was measured, the dielectric strength of the capacitor was measured in accordance with ASTM standard D149-97a. Both tests are performed on the same sample setup as illustrated in Figure 5, where the exposed carbon fiber and gold coated BST are covered with silver paint and connected to testing leads.

Fig. 5. Schematic of the electrode configuration for the multifunctional fiber breakdown strength and dielectric testing.

3.3 Energy density testing

For dielectric ceramics such as BST, the dielectric constant is a function of temperature and peaks at the Curie point due to the existence of free moving dipoles in the crystal at the Curie point T_c . The Curie temperature of BST can be altered by the ratio of barium and strontium and can be linearly described as [21]

$$T_c = -195 + 322.2x, \quad (3)$$

where T_c (°C) is the Curie temperature of BST and x is the fraction of barium ions in the BST composition. According to equation (2), the capacitance has a linear relationship with the relative dielectric constant and therefore the capacitance of the multifunctional fiber should be influenced by the barium and strontium ratio of the BST films. From Equation (3), $\text{Ba}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{TiO}_3$ has a T_c around room temperature, which results in an extremely high dielectric constant. [20] The high dielectric constant is believed to be a result of the displacement of the Ti ion from the center of the oxygen octahedron. BST has a cubic structure at room temperature for $x < 0.3$ but becomes tetragonal for $x > 0.3$. When $x = 0.3$, the crystal structure of BST transits in between cubic and tetragonal, leaving a large spontaneous dipole and leading to high dielectric constant near the T_c .

Theoretically, the dielectric constant of BST varies from one thousand to more than ten thousand as the composition to changes. [20, 21] Therefore, in order to verify the quality of our fabricated BST films, after the capacitance is measured, the dielectric constant of each sample is calculated according to Equation (2) and plotted in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Relative dielectric constant of BST films as a function of BST composition.

As can be seen in Figure 6, the dielectric constant of BST ranges from 578 to 2854, and peaks at a composition of $\text{Ba}_{0.71}\text{Sr}_{0.29}\text{TiO}_3$ since the T_c is closest to ambient. However, the dielectric constant is lower than other previously published data. Several possible reasons for this relatively low dielectric constant exist, such as the roughness of the BST surface as indicated in Figure 2, and the possibility of a small portion of TiO_2 impurities which may significantly reduce the dielectric. However, the dielectric constant of certain BSTs such as $\text{Ba}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{TiO}_3$ and $\text{Ba}_{0.71}\text{Sr}_{0.29}\text{TiO}_3$ are more than twice higher than that of BTO, leading to the potential for developing multifunctional structures with significantly enhanced energy storage capacity.

Following the measurement of the dielectric constant for each sample, dielectric strength testing was performed to characterize the energy storage capacity of the fiber. The dielectric strength is calculated by dividing the breakdown voltage by the thickness of BST coating and is shown in Figure 7. The dielectric strength first increases then decreases with an increasing fraction of barium ions, with a

maximum at $\text{Ba}_{0.71}\text{Sr}_{0.29}\text{TiO}_3$. This trend can be explained by the phase transformation between cubic and tetragonal crystal structures. It has been shown that the breakdown strength of BTO also peaks around the T_c due to this phase transition. [22]

Fig. 7. Breakdown strength of BST films as a function of BST composition.

According to Equations (1) and (2), the energy density is a function of the dielectric constant, sample geometry, and breakdown voltage. All tested samples have similar geometry and the dielectric constant and breakdown strength show a similar trend; therefore, the energy density for each fiber should have a similar trend. The energy densities for each fiber are calculated and presented in Figure 8. The BST composition with the highest energy density occurs with $\text{Ba}_{0.71}\text{Sr}_{0.29}\text{TiO}_3$ or when the T_c is at ambient temperature, with an average energy density of 0.1202J/cc. Compared to other structural capacitors appearing in the literature, the energy density is higher or comparable to most of them. [16] The novel multifunctional fiber utilizes the carbon fiber as both the inner electrode and the load-bearing component, allowing easy integration into existing high performance carbon fiber composites. Our previously developed structural capacitor based on SiC fiber is limited to single fiber fabrication and is challenging to scale to a composites level fabrication. Since the aspect ratio was not considered here and was shown to be a

major factor in the performance of the SiC fibers, the energy density of the carbon based structural capacitor is more than 5 times higher than that of the SiC based capacitor at the same aspect ratio. [16] It is then believed that using thinner BST coatings could significantly increase the energy density of this carbon fiber based structural capacitor by reducing the electric field density at the inner electrode.

Fig. 8. Energy density of multifunctional fibers as a function of BST composition.

4 Conclusions

Multifunctional composites are a new class of material developed to reduce system complexity by integrating one or more performance related functionalities into a load bearing structure. One of the most widely studied functionalities is energy storage, aiming to enhance the efficiency and operational life of the system or its components. This paper characterized the energy storage properties of a structural capacitor composed of a carbon fiber with barium strontium titanate coating. The carbon fiber acts as a load bearing material as well as an inner electrode for the dielectric coating. Various compositions of barium strontium titanate films were tested and the highest energy density was determined to occur when the T_c was close to ambient. It is shown that its energy density is higher than that of most of the structural capacitors developed thus far, demonstrating a strong potential for this type of multifunctional fiber to provide structural composites with embedded energy storage properties.

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